

8 Theory and the D'alembert Variation

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Abstract:

By using the new framework of the 8-theory and the recent insight about the phenomena of quark confinement, it is possible to represent the result in the context of analytical theories with a modern variation. The variation will explain the phenomena of quark confinement from a different view. The quark confinement will be described within the main equation of the 8 theory, which used to describe dark energy and Quark manifesting.

Introduction

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial \partial g'}{\partial \partial t} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\delta g \rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$N \in \mathbb{R}, N \rightarrow \infty \quad (3)$$

$$-\delta g' \rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^N -\delta g'_i = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i - \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g'_i = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \partial E_i / \partial t - \sum_{i=1}^N \partial E^2_i / \partial^2 t = 0 \quad (6)$$

The sum of all arbitrary variations and accelerations is summed as zero in this framework. Similar to the procedure D'alembert taken with forces and accelerations. That is an additional take on the phenomena of quark confinement, published earlier by the author.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)